

Book Review/ News/ Views/ Comments

Healthcare Reform in India– Some Policy Implications

Hiranmoy Chattopadhyaya*, TK Chatterjee

CMJ University, Meghalaya, India

India's healthcare picture seems to be at crucial stage, where there are some positive achievements on the health indicators but suffers some serious shortcomings in care delivery. The country has been successful in eradicating polio, reducing epidemics caused by tropical diseases and controlled HIV to a large extent. However, it still faces a huge economic burden due to communicable and non-communicable diseases (NCDs), struggles to balance accessibility, affordability and quality and in hiking public health budgets.

Meanwhile, healthcare has become one of [India's largest sectors](#), both in terms of revenue and employment. Research by Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu India indicates the size of the industry will reach \$160 billion by 2017 and [\\$280 billion](#) by 2020. But despite this growth, India's healthcare sector faces numerous challenges in trying to effectively serve its 1.3 billion population. Here are challenges in care deliveries that need to be addressed.

CHALLENGES IN CARE DELIVERY IN INDIA:

1. NEGLECT OF RURAL POPULATION:

- According to a [KPMG report](#), with the higher spending power of consumers in towns and cities the majority of Indian healthcare professionals are concentrated around urban areas, leaving rural areas under served.
- While India meets the global average in number of physicians, nearly 75% of dispensaries, 60% of hospitals and 80% of doctors are located in urban areas. Doctors cater to a third of the urban population, or no more than 442 million people.
- Availability of 31.5% of hospitals and 16% hospital beds for 75% of total population residing in rural areas.
- Professional doctors reluctant to serve in rural areas.

2. SOCIAL INEQUALITY:

- Highly imbalanced in India – under served in rural, hilly and remote area and well developed in urban areas and cities.
- SC/ST and downtrodden people – far away from modern health facility.

3. INADEQUATE OUTLAY FOR HEALTH:

- Low health standards due to India spends just [4.7%](#) of GDP on healthcare (2014), whereas China spends 5.6 times more, with the U.S. 125 times more.
- Around [62%](#) of health expenses incurred by Indians was met using personal savings, called "out-of-

pocket expenses," compared with 13.4% in the U.S., 10% in the UK and 54% in China.

- Only 17.3% public expenditure on health whereas that is 24.9% in China, 45.4% in Sri Lanka and 44.1% in USA.

4. SHORTAGE OF MEDICAL PERSONNEL:

- Basic problem – shortage of doctors and nurses – 1 government doctor for every 10,189 people (WHO recommends 1:1000). In comparison to these, the US has [24.5](#) doctors for every 10,000 people and one hospital bed for every 345 citizens.
- Out of 1 million doctors in the country, only 10% of them work in the public health sector. While urban areas have [58% qualified doctors](#), in rural areas the number is as low as 18.8%.
- Workforce unevenly distributed - 20 health workers per 10,000 population, with allopathic doctors comprising 31% of the workforce, nurses and midwives 30%, pharmacists 11%, AYUSH practitioners 9%, and others 9%.
- Vacant Posts - About 10.4% of the sanctioned posts of auxiliary nurse midwives are vacant, which rises to 40.7% of the posts of male health workers. 27% of doctor posts at PHCs were vacant, which is more than a quarter of the sanctioned posts.
- Absenteeism - Nearly 40 % of the doctors and other health service providers are found to be absent from their posts on a typical working day. While absenteeism among doctors varied between 30 % in MP to as high as 67% in Bihar.

5. INADEQUATE BASIC INFRASTRUCTURE:

- Public Health Centres (PHCs) lack basic infrastructural facilities such as beds, wards, toilets, drinking water, clean labour rooms for delivery, and regular electricity.
- Only one government hospital bed per 2046 people, and one state-run hospital per 90,343 people.
- in rural areas, only 37% of people are able to access healthcare facilities within a 5km distance, and 68% were able to access out-patient facilities.

6. PARTIAL USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY:

- Absence of Hospital Management System ERP including Supply Change Management (SCM) and Customer Relation Management (CRM).
- Limited application of Tele-medicine.

* Corresponding Author-
Hiranmoy Chattopadhyaya, CMJ University, Meghalaya
hiranmoy@yahoo.com

- Nonexistence of Analytics to analyse the condition of the patient in much better ways and suggest recommendations accordingly for early relief and recovery.

7. EXPENSIVE HEALTH SERVICE:

- Quite expensive health services.
- High price of essential drugs.

8. MISTRUST BETWEEN PATIENTS - HEALTHCARE SERVICE PROVIDERS:

- Trust Deficit – Low quality of care delivery (infected with some other illness after leaving hospital due to improper sanitation), high treatment package, poor post hospitalization support, etc.
- Feel Exploited – Take advantages of both patients' critical condition and medical insurance sum assured.
- Less Accountability – Negligence in attending patients as well as constant monitoring and post treatment updates.

9. POLLUTED ENVIRONMENT:

- Arsenic & Fluoride free and germless drinking water.
- Pollution-free clean air.
- Maintain clean surroundings.

10. UNINFORMED HEALTH AWARENESS:

- Breast feeding practice.
- Reproductive health issue.
- Mother & Childcare.
- Cleanliness.
- Common cause of prevalent illness and their prevention.

11. LOW LEVELS HEALTH INSURANCE:

- Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) has stated that India's per capita healthcare expenditure is one of the lowest levels of the world.
- Government's contribution to insurance stands at roughly 32%, as opposed to 83.5% in the UK.
- [76%](#) of Indians do not have health insurance, this results in the high out-of-pocket
- expenses incurred by the citizens of this country.

12. HIGH-END MEDICAL EDUCATION:

- Long innings - Minimum 15 years (5 years MBBS, 3 years MD, 3 years specialization, 4 years in gaining experience) spent in growing as an established Medical practitioner.
- Abnormal unaffordable Expenses - Controlled mostly by private Medical colleges –charging over Rs.1 crore for MBBS and Rs.2-3 crore for PG seats.

13. LIMITED MEDICAL RESEARCH:

- Low fund allocated for medical research.
- No comprehensive plan to research & manufacture life-saving drugs.
- Limited research on alternative medicines – Ayurveda, Unani and Homeopathy.

14. EMPHASIS ON TRADITIONAL METHOD:

- Follow mostly service based 'Western Model' hospitals.
- Neglected preventive, pro-motive, rehabilitative and public health measures.
- Promotion of traditional therapy including Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Unani and Alternative medicines.

15. INEFFICIENT STATUTORY REGULATION FOR MONITORING PRIVATE HEALTH SECTOR:

- Not a single statutory body responsible for registration of private hospital, nursinghome, clinic, diagnostic lab and even pharmaceutical industry.
- Controlling bodies are virtual and non-functioning.
- Weak provisions in various Acts.
- Heavily influenced by private health sector.
- Operates without any significant controls and restrictions.

Since the magnitude of these challenges is significant, these cannot be resolved by the government alone. In order to strengthen healthcare delivery and improve business prospects, policy makers, healthcare providers, business leaders, technology providers and pharma companies will need to devise strategies that transforms a sea-change in sustainable care delivery where mutually trusted public-private partnership may be the best way to solve India's healthcare problems with win-win ventures.

HEALTHCARE REFORM SUGGESTED:

1. RIGHT TO INSURED:

- Parliament to enact 'Right to Insured' Act wherein every Indian family shall be covered under Ayushman Bharat - National Health Protection Mission (AB-NHPM).
- A defined annual benefit cover of Rs. 5.00 lakh per family (on a family floater basis) plus Rs.5.00 lakh accidental benefits under AB-NHPM to over fifteen (15) crore beneficiary including poor, deprived rural families and identified occupational categories of urban workers' families appearing in either latest SECC Database or under existing RSBY Beneficiary Families or family income less than Rs.1.2 lacs yearly or less than Rs.10000 monthly will be considered for deciding the eligible automatic beneficiary families without paying annual premium.
- Remaining ten (10) crore families whose yearly income is over Rs.1.2 lacs will also be brought under AB-NHPM scheme paying an annual premium @ Rs.1375/- per family (considering insurance premium per family @ Rs.500 for healthcare and Rs.50 for accidental benefits - Rs.550 x 25 crore/10 crore = Rs.1375) which will cover premiums of 15 crore beneficiary families also. Family means husband wife and their dependent children.
- The annual healthcare and accidental benefit amount of group family insurance may be enhanced to Rs.7 lakh + 10 lakh, and Rs.10 lakh + Rs.15 lakh increasing premium proportionately at Rs.1955/- (Insurance

premium @ Rs.1855 for healthcare and Rs.100 for accidental benefits) and Rs.2800/- (Insurance premium @ Rs.2650 for healthcare and Rs.150 for accidental benefits) respectively. However, premium figures will totally dependent upon online open bidding by insurance providers.

- Individuals or their families or group of individuals under group family insurance can also avail Superior Grade AB-NHPM scheme or separate insurance schemes not under AB-NHPM paying higher premiums where facilities and quality of service will be enhanced accordingly satisfying their requirements.
- However, premiums of all staff/employees of both Central as well as State Governments including MLAs & MPs will be borne by the respective Government Considering total government employees at 2.25 crore, the total expenditure on premiums for government employees would be approx. Rs.3100 crore.
- Similarly, all staff/employees of PSU/Private Organizations including MNC, MSME, SSI, Contractors, Private School/College staff, etc. will also come under AB-NHPM scheme and the total expenditure on premium for public/private employees will be borne by respective PSU/private organization.
- Expenses of various healthcare schemes including ESI, Mediclaim, expenditure on hospitalization, etc. compensated by governments and private organizations will be stopped after introducing AB-NHPM scheme resulting huge saving in expenditure on healthcare of both government, public and private sectors.
- The prevailing 100% IT Tax benefits given to individuals for Mediclaim will be withdrawn resulting considerable increase in IT tax collection.
- Insurance Regulatory & Development Authority of India (IRDAI) should act as the harmonious bridge amongst patients, hospital and Insurance Companies to address their issues professionally.
- Preliminary discussions with private Insurance Companies (HDFC Ergo, Max Bhupa, ICICI Lombard, etc.) indicate that they are excited to associate with this project.

2. RESTRUCTURING & GRADING IN HEALTHCARE DELIVERY FACILITIES:

Once every Indian is insured under AB-NHPM, it is possible to bring structural changes in hospital services and management. Here are insights from healthcare services that can lead India towards a healthy tomorrow.

3 - TIER HEALTHCARE DELIVERY SYSTEM: - It is reported on 31.03.2019 that a total of 25778 Public Hospitals, 24,855 Rural Public Health Centres (RPHCs) and 5,190 Urban Public Health Centres (UPHCs) have been functional in the country. While one state run hospital gives care to about 90000 patients, RPHC & UPSC handle about 20000 - 30000 patients. It has been observed that public hospitals and public health centres are not only over-crowded but also can't attend outpatient department (OPD) comprehensively particularly who are visiting from interior villages where even primary or preventive healthcare services are absent or limited.

To deal with this appalling situation particularly for those patients residing in remote villages, a three-tiered healthcare system may be introduced. While existing RPHCs & UPHCs and public hospitals are supporting Tier - 2 and Tier -3 healthcare systems respectively, Tier - 1 - Rural Primary & Preventive Health Centres (RPPHCs) will be required to be set up within 5 Km radius covering maximum 10000 population. The total number of RPPHCs set-up will be about 60000 considering 65.53% of Indian population live in rural India (reported in 2019) to cater additional 60 crore population leaving the existing 24855 RHCs which handles about 25 crore rural population residing nearby.

RURAL PRIMARY & PREVENTATIVE HEALTH CENTRES (RPPHCs): -

The infrastructure and supporting facilities of RPPHCs will be such that it can adequately accommodate primary healthcare services. Individuals/self-employed will be asked to invest in developing such infrastructure & facilities including a rentalspace of about 2000 sq ft for Waiting Room, OPD, Labour Room, Lab, 10 beds Patient Treatment Room and Toilet. In every RPPHC, 24x7 service will be provided recruiting 4 trained staff, preferably local, out of which the investor or his deputed person will be one of them who will also look after day-to-day management of the RPPHC. Out with pregnancy labour and delivery knowledge. All 4 staffs with minimum HS qualification will first be trained for 4 - 6 months with 15 days practical & computer training for efficiently handling primary healthcare services and providing preventative healthcare awareness. Online professional training and an annual licensing exam will be organized to further enhance their skill. These trained paramedic staff will be designated as Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA). These trained staffs will also make door-to-door campaigns for healthcare preventive awareness which will substantially reduce treatment cost. Insurance Companies should also invest in this awareness programme to keep citizens ailment free.

The initial investment in setting up the infrastructure is estimated at Rs.3.0 lacs - Rs.0.5 lac for essential medical accessories (beds, oxygen cylinders, nebulizers, oxy meters, BP measuring instrument, thermometer, saline stand, etc); Rs.0.3 lac for medicines, surgical and stationary; Rs. 1.5 lac for Lab equipment (ECG, Calorimeter, Incubator, Centrifuge, Microscope, Kits & others) and Computer & Printer; Rs.0.7 lacs for DG Set/inverter, Fridge, Internets, electric lines, etc. The monthly operating expenses would be Rs.1.0 lac including Rs.45K towards salary of 4 trained staffs and sweeper, Rs.30K for consumables, Rs.5K rent, Rs.8 K for interest and repayment of investment and Rs.2K for miscellaneous.

All medical accessories, medicines, consumables, etc. will be indented after submitting monthly consumption and stock position and sent by respective centralized authority purchasing from centralized e-procurement portal promoted by the central government. The medicines, especially generic may also be procured from 'Pradhan Mantri Bhatiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP)' launched a couple of years back by the present government. Already 6510 such counters are functioning,

and similar counters may be opened in each UPHCs/RPHCs.

All medical advice will be given through telemedicine and video conferences. Weekly visits of General Physician (Allopathic, Homeopathic & Ayurveda), ENT, Eye and Dentist will be arranged who will come from nearby public hospital or UPHC/RPHC.

24x7 Ambulance service will be available from nearby RPHC/UPHC to transfer critical patients first to UPHC/RHPC and only the most seriously ill patients should be referred to the third and final Tier, the public/private hospitals/nursing homes. RPPHC & RHPC – the two lower-level tiers made up the ‘Collective Health System’ are adequate to provide most of the country’s medical care for downtrodden people.

➤ **OPD Expenses:** - The annual expenditure to run these RPPHCs would be around Rs.8000 crore inclusive of 10% contingency considering monthly OPD expenses @Rs.1 lac. Similarly, OPD expenses of approx.30000 UPHCs & RPHCs would be another Rs.8000 crore considering monthly OPD costs @ Rs.2 lacs per unit + 10% contingencies. Similarly, free OPD service will be given by public hospitals only to those 15 crore families who got AB-NHPM schemes without paying any annual premium. They must show their different colour AB-NHPM Card to the concerned authorities to avail free OPD services. Other patients will require to pay consultancy fees to doctors and cost of medicines and lab tests as prescribed by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory. The OPD expenses in about 26000 public hospitals would be roughly Rs.15500 crore considering monthly expenses at Rs.5 lacs including 10% contingency per hospital. It is thus estimated that total expenditure towards OPD by the government would be Rs.31500 crore which maybe shared between centre and states at the ratio of 60:40.

REGULATORY AUTHORITY: - Central & State Healthcare Regulatory Authority (HDA) and Apex Bodies under them will be promoted through legislations giving full authority of management & control of all aspects and all types of healthcare organizations including Hospitals, Medical Colleges, Medical Research Institutes, Start-ups, Public Health Centres, Rural Primary Health Centres, Clinics, Diagnostic Labs, Pharmaceutical Industries, Medical Shops, Insurance Companies and any other agency involved in care deliveries. Central & State Healthcare Regulatory Authorities should function coherently without interference of the government. These Regulatory Authorities will be autonomous, accountable, and creditworthy.

✓ **Formation of Central & State Regulatory Authority:-** Both Central and State Regulatory Authorities should have maximum 15 members selected from highly educated and experienced professionals with management and academic exposure having minimum 20-25 years of experiences particularly in the field of: setting up and managing of Hospital & Medical Institutes (Allopathy, Homeopathy, Ayurveda, etc.), Pathology, Medical Engineering, Clinical Trial & Research, Pharma Industry, Exposure in Insurance Products, Innovative ideas in social

engineering movement, Planning & Strategy formulation, Total quality & productive management (TQM/TPM), Human resource development & training, Cost & financial engineering, Environment & social science; Women & Childcare.

✓ **Formation of Apex Body** – The Regulatory Authority shall monitor efficiently & effectively by distributing its responsibilities to a large number of Apex Bodies, each of which will control about 500 healthcare deliveries consisting of about 100 hospitals/clinics/diagnostic centres, 100 rural PHCs, 20 urban PHCs and 350 RPPHCs or approx. 10 million population located in various districts of a state in order to cater quality professional services and exchanging specialized knowledge. Medical shops and pharma industries in that area will also come under their surveillance. Each Apex Body should have maximum 10 members with the same background as the members of the Centre/State Regulatory Body but with lesser experiences.

Once these Regulatory Authorities are empowered, the workload and responsibility of Health Ministries of both Centre and States/UT will be minimal, and they will just work as ‘Watch Dog’ and set guidelines from time to time for further transparency.

Major Responsibility without Limitations of Regulatory Authority –

- ✓ Appointment of members of the State Healthcare Regulatory Authority by the Centre Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Identify and amalgamate 500 healthcare service providers under one Apex Body within a state by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Appointment of members of Apex Body by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Promotion, increment and transfer of doctors/nurses by the Apex Body/ Centre/ State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Appoint Evaluation Experts for grading healthcare units by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Evaluation of public & private hospitals/nursing homes and UPHCs/RPHCs for appropriate grading by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Selection of Insurance Companies for offering AB-NHPM insurance packages to families by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Grade-wise fixing of treatment package by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Fixing of price of generic and other medicines & medical devices of pharma companies by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Settlement of disputed claims by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority in consultation with IRDIA.
- ✓ Online approval for opening of new medical college cum hospital and research centre and start-ups by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Fix admission & teaching fees in public & private medical institutes evaluating their grading,

infrastructure, academic excellence, research, patents, etc.

- ✓ Approval for technology transfer for manufacturing medical devices in India.
- ✓ Recommend FDI funding in building healthcare infrastructure and services.
- ✓ Monitor all Apex Bodies by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Launch IPO to raise fund for Public Hospitals jointly under one apex Body or individually by the Apex Body.
- ✓ Evaluation of doctors & staff through online 360-degree feedback from stakeholders by the Apex Body.
- ✓ Monitor fund distribution by the Centre/State Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Introduction of Digital technologies in healthcare services by the Centre/ State Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Healthcare innovation exploration by the Centre/State Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Interpret & analyse of data/information and recommend future goal by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Online/offline training of doctors/nurses/paramedic staff like Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA).
- ✓ Promote Ayurveda & Homeopathy teaching & research by the Centre/State Regulatory Authority.
- ✓ Encourage Medical Tourism by the Centre/State Healthcare Regulatory Authority providing digital platform and ease of doing business to attract more and more foreign patients across the world.

PUBLIC HOSPITALS: - Apex Bodies and their connected public hospitals, UPHCs/RPHCs and RPPHCs should be brought under Section 8 of Companies Act, 2013 (erstwhile Section 25 of Companies Act, 1956) and should function like Public Sector Undertakings (PSUs). Their 49% shares (maximum) may be floated through IPO to general public to raise fund for revamping them. Public healthcare deliveries must be equally competitive like private hospitals in terms of accessibility, affordability, quality and deliveries. Proposed restructuring of public healthcare systems are:

- ✓ Public hospitals should be managed by a professional manager (like CMD in PSUs) having vast exposure in managing hospitals/hotels who will also guide UPHCs/RPHCs & RPPHCs connected with them.
- ✓ Toilet & drain cleaning, waste management & patient movement & other services of Group C & D staffs should be outsourced on contractual basis to receive quality services. Existing Group – C & D staffs, if interested, may be allowed to form a cooperative to take these contractual jobs to enhance their monthly income. However, there should be no direct recruitment of Group C & D staffs in future. All contractual staffs will be brought under social security schemes including AB-NHPM (free), PF, Gratuity, Atal Pension Yojana (Rs.5000/- per month after attaining 60 years), Unorganized Sector Pension scheme (Rs.3000/- per

month after attaining 60 years), etc. deducting premium from their monthly salary.

- ✓ The inventory should be controlled and management through cloud computing Hospital Management System ERP.
- ✓ All medicines, toiletries, chemicals, surgery tools & equipment, lab equipment, etc. should be centralized procured through e-procurement GeM portal with e- reverse auction option, promoted for public procurement for the government of India. Hospitals to raise their indents in the **centralized e-procurement portal** to get highly competitive prices for procuring large volume of same items indented by various hospitals and selected vendors to despatch the material to the respective hospital directly at a very competitive price when all payments will be made through online to maintain maximum transparency.
- ✓ Charges for Doctors, medicines and tests for outdoor patients of outpatient departments (OPDs) of Public Hospitals, UPHCs/RPHCs and RPPHCs will be complimentary for 15 crore families whose premiums for AB-NHPM scheme are provided by third parties. However, remaining 10 crore families who pay their premiums for AB-NHPM scheme themselves have to pay all OPD expenses to Public Hospitals/UPHCs/RPHCs/ RPPHCs billed by respective departments.
- ✓ The CTC (Cost to Company) of doctors/nurses/other staffs should be revised and market driven depending on their qualifications, experiences, specialization, job descriptions, etc. to enhance their productivity and quality services at par with private hospitals.
- ✓ Hourly rate of every doctors/nurse should be derived considering working hours at 200 per months. The gross salary should be divided into two parts – fixed (75% of total gross salary) and floating (25% of total gross salary) based on their performance evaluation.
- ✓ The monthly & annually performance of doctors and nurses will be evaluated using 360-degree appraisal tool taking online feedback from all stakeholders – patients/service takers, colleagues, bosses and subordinates/service givers.
- ✓ Regular online training and exams of doctors and nurses will be conducted by global experts to enhance their skill and knowledge. Their promotion and increment will also be based on their performance analysis.
- ✓ Specialized doctors may be associated with the hospitals as consultant and attend patients on call. Their consultancy fees should be fixed on hourly or per patient basis depending on their market value.
- ✓ **PRIVATE HEALTHCARE SERVICES:** - Similarly, all Private Hospitals, Nursing Homes, Clinics, Diagnostic Centres, Testing Labs, Pharmaceutical Industries, Medical Shops, etc. should also be brought under the Central or State Healthcare Regulatory Authority with strong provisions to regulate them transparently and professionally.
- ✓ **GRADING OF HEALTHCARE SERVICES:** - Healthcare services particularly Public & Private Hospitals/Nursing Homes and

UPHCs/RPHCS are mandatorily required to be graded by expert teams entrusted by the Regulatory Authority. All hospitals/nursinghomes and UPHCs/RPHCs will be graded using Hospital Management ERP Tool evaluating their infrastructure & facilities available and also online 360-degree feedback from stakeholders every after 6 months. The price structure of treatment& operation package of hospitals/nursing homes and UPHCs/RPHCs will be fixed depending on their grading. Similarly, price range of laboratory testing will be evaluated by expert teams (entrusted by the Regulatory Authority) considering all cost aspects related to individual tests. All diagnostic centres and clinics will be guided to fix their charges within those ranges recommended by the expert team.

✓ **INSURANCE PACKAGE:** - Expert team (entrusted by the Regulatory Authority)together with representatives of insurance companies, hospitals/nursing homes andpharma manufacturers will determine the cost of medicines and medical accessories for pharma manufacturers. Pharma manufacturers are liable to sale their products to hospitals/nursing homes and UPHCs/RPHCs at the prices fixed by the expert team.The same expert team will also determine the total package value of various treatments for different grade of hospitals/nursing homes and UPHCs/RPHCs based on cost of medicines and medical accessories and all other cost related aspects including consultancy charges of specialist doctors. Hospitals and nursing homes are liable to accept those insurance packages as determined by the expert team for availing AB-NHPM schemes by patients.

✓ The fixed prices of medicines & medical accessories and treatment packages shouldbe such that all stakeholders including insurance companies, hospitals/nursing homes and UPHCs/RPHCs and pharma manufacturers can make reasonable profits to sustain and expand their social entrepreneurship businesses.

MANDATORILY USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES: -

✓ National Health Mission launched Health ID linked with Aadhaar or mobile number of individuals for creating safer and efficient digital health records which can be presented to healthcare service providers to receive lab reports, prescriptions, and diagnosis digitally.

✓ ‘Digital Technologies’ should be mandatorily used in all Hospitals/nursing homes and UPHCs/RPHCs/RPPHCs and even private practitioners for greater efficiency & transparency in healthcare delivery. Electronic Medical Record (EMR), digital version of physical medical record, information sharing across caregivers (hospitals, diagnostic lab, pharmacy, etc.) as well as patients’ parties playing acrucial role in optimizing patient care. It will help to develop improved medicines and drug dosage combinations, screen patients better, detect diseases early, perform complex surgical interventions, etc.

✓ Mandatorily use of cloud computing ‘Healthcare ERP’ on SaaS (Software as a Service) basis against a nominal annual rent.

✓ Another ‘Wearable technology’ is facilitating seamless and accurate health monitoring. Wearable devices supported by mobile technology, can now allow a doctor to monitor a patient’s vitals remotely. This technology has in-built patient monitoring devices which provide information on heart rhythm, blood pressure, breathing patterns and blood glucose level, etc.

✓ ‘Telemedicine’ is another channel which immensely benefit to patients in remote locations. Offering convenience, it helps them to gain access to doctors without physical travel. This helps in better management of chronic diseases and consistent post-operative monitoring.

✓ ‘AI’ is a major technological breakthrough for the medical space. It allows for the creation of a personalised environment for both patients as well as healthcare providers. Many healthcare experts anticipate that operationalising AI will result in a 10 to 15 per cent increase in productivity.

✓ Mentioning further innovations, ‘Big Data’ is another area which will allow for preventive care. It will also allow for analytical solutions which will give insight into treatment viability, drug utilisation and self-care programmes, specific to chronic conditions.

✓ ‘Blockchain’ will bring healthcare efficiencies by providing transparency in process, eliminating intermediaries wherever possible, providing a guard against counterfeit drugs and reducing unnecessary healthcare costs.

✓ Rapid developments in mobile technologies, cloud computing, digital imaging, machine learning and 3-D printing have paved the way for breakthroughs in the development and adoption of healthcare technologies – from telemedicine to nanotechnology, lab-grown 3-D organs to internet of things and electronic healthrecords to AI. Besides, the use of data to build India-centric research (most of the research in the medical field is largely based on the Caucasian samples) is possible only through digitalisation.

✓ Apart from clinical decision support tools, digital tools can make clinical expertise available either remotely or through expertise embedded in medical equipment. The examples include digital pathology, tele-radiology, point of care diagnostic devices, tele-consultation, etc. The second issue is to keep millions of frontline health workers updated about the latest knowledge and skills, where e-learning academies and virtual classrooms can be of great help. Thirdly, these can help in enhancing the quality and effectiveness of care being delivered on the ground by paramedic staff like Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA) workers through the use of appropriate apps on e-pads/mobile phones.

✓ **BOOSTING OF MEDICAL TOURISM:**

-Both public & private hospitals in India will be given all supporting structures and services to encourage ‘Medical Tourism’ in a big way which

will not only create huge employment opportunity but also improve their bottom lines. Foreign patients in large numbers visiting India mainly from the Middle East, Africa, Pakistan and Bangladesh For paediatric, cardiac surgery, liver transplants, etc. and also from UK, Europe and North America for coronary bypass or orthopaedic treatments for relatively cheaper specialized private healthcare.

✓ INVESTMENT IN HEALTHCARE

SERVICES: - Government of India should allow 100% FDI in healthcare sectors to build specialty hospital and academic & research institute by renowned global hospital/academic chains and also in manufacturing of high value imported medical devices & appliances (currently around 80% imported) in India. Besides, Healthcare Regulatory Authorities should encourage various public and religious trusts to invest in creating facilities for healthcare services in particularly rural and semi-urban areas. CSR fund should also be invested in this area.

Since low-cost ancient Indian Ayurveda treatments have huge domestic and export potential, Regulatory Authority should encourage religious trusts & big houses giving various incentives to invest handsomely in creating Ayurveda research & teaching centres with vast plantation of medicinal plants to make India its global hub.

✓ EXPANSION OF MEDICAL START-UP:

- It is good sign to notice that many young entrepreneurs are investing recently in medical start-up ventures: -

- ✓ Some start-ups have taken initiatives in opening a chain of retail pharmacies which dispense only quality generic drugs at a fraction of the cost.
- ✓ To enable medical services to reach rural areas, 'A3RMT' and 'Neurosynaptic Communications' are manufacturing light-weight equipment for measuring [ECG](#), blood pressure, heart rate, auscultation, oxygen saturation and the temperature of a patient. It then transmits data wirelessly to doctors anywhere in the world. These machines perform quick diagnostics with little medical training and rely heavily on their patented technology to work in low-bandwidth locations in far flung corners of the country.
- ✓ 'A3RMT' has assisted in effective treatment of more than 56,000 patients in 450 locations in India and saved more than 2,000 lives through emergency intervention whereas 'Neurosynaptic Communications' has helped treat around 250,000 patients in 2,300 villages last year alone.
- ✓ To ensure transparency in the treatment of patients, 'Credihealth' is a medical support start-up that gives guidance to the patient, from the first consultation to each stage of the treatment process. It also helps patients to find the right doctor, book appointments, request cost estimates for procedures, and helps to manage the admissions and discharge process.

- ✓ 'Affordplan' is an Innovative Financial Savings Platform, who helps prospective patients in planning tailor-made solution for non-emergency medical procedures
- ✓ such as those related to pregnancy, eye care, dental, plastic surgeries,
- ✓ orthopaedic, genetic testing and so on. Affordplan allows to choose a hospital
- ✓ and decide the saving plan to deposit online on a daily, weekly, or monthly basis
- ✓ to hospital. Once a patient completes the savings plan, can easily avail the
- ✓ medical treatment without the burden of upfront one-time payment.
- ✓ Another start-up 'Myupchar' gives users a range of information on [Ayurveda](#),
- ✓ [Homeopathy](#) and [Allopathy](#) treatment, to address various health and wellness-related issues, including obesity, pregnancy, women's health and post-surgery care.
- ✓ Other start-up 'GrowFitter' focused on improving the fitness level is a machine learning-powered platform that directs its users to multiple fitness options including yoga, dance, and kickboxing.

There is an opportunity for India to skip a full generation and transform healthcare and care delivery empowering professionals to manage them using digital technology. Healthcare can learn so many things from new-age businesses and transform India if the government takes the back seat giving full authority to Regulatory Authority to run the healthcare businesses aiming at enhancing quality, accountability, transparency, patient satisfaction and efficiency in care delivery.